

Two Forces, Two Energies and Special Relativity for a Radiating Charge?

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Newtonian mechanics introduces a potential $V(\mathbf{r})$ which represents energy, but at the same time is associated with a force through $\mathbf{F} = -\text{grad } V(\mathbf{r})$. In other words, this force is due to changes in energy $V(\mathbf{r})$ in space. A point charge, which has rest mass, can be accelerated due to a force. According to special relativity rest mass is equivalent to energy and so accelerated energy is now a second kind of force. In fact, if $V(\mathbf{r})$ is energy, then one would expect that this energy may be accelerated giving rise to this second kind of force (which is not gradient dependent). At this point, there is one energy ($V(\mathbf{r})$) created by a source with rest mass) and two kinds of forces, one gradient dependent and the second existing only if the source (with rest mass) is accelerated.

An issue arises if one considers the two kinds of forces, $-\text{grad } V(\mathbf{r})$ (or its Lorentz corrected form) and $V(\mathbf{r}) dv/dt$ (symbolic form), where dv/dt is acceleration. {Here, we are being somewhat simplistic in writing $V(\mathbf{r}) dv/dt$. This is not the exact expression, but symbolically shows that there is no extra gradient acting on $V(\mathbf{r})$.} The point we wish to make is that $-\text{grad } V(\mathbf{r})$ and $V(\mathbf{r}) dv/dt$ have very different spatial drop-offs if $V(\mathbf{r})$ goes as $1/r$ (positive power). As a result, a person measuring force would notice $V(\mathbf{r}) dv/dt$ if the source of $V(\mathbf{r})$ is accelerating. Given the slow drop-off, the measurer would not associate this force with $-\text{grad } V(\mathbf{r})$ and so would think that it possibly comes from a different source independent of the object creating $V(\mathbf{r})$. In other words, it is possible to take a source which creates $V(\mathbf{r})$ and accelerate it. This leads to the usual $-\text{grad } V(\mathbf{r})$ (Lorentz corrected) which is linked to the source object and second piece of energy and momentum which also represents force and has broken off from the source, and is linked with $V(\mathbf{r}) dv/dt$.

The question arises: Why should there be this second source of energy? We argue that it is anticipated from special relativity. If one creates a Lorentz transformation for a particle with rest mass, (presumably a source of $V(\mathbf{r})$), then the formulation involves a parameter b (units of speed) which is the same as seen in all frames. It is described by $E=pc$ which is linked to the wave equation $\text{velocity} = b = \text{frequency} \cdot \text{wavelength}$ and $x=bt$. It seems that this speed b is an upper bound speed and frame independent and so seems to be similar to that of a wave. The b object is a special one which does not have rest mass, but has energy and momentum. If there is no medium associated with b , then by Newton's action-reaction one would expect some kind of force to be present as well. The question then becomes: What kind of forces are these which create a kind of wave which has a maximum speed? From the previous paragraph, we considered a general $V(\mathbf{r})$ associated with a particle with rest mass. Then $V(\mathbf{r})$ is created by the source particle, but we noted that if acceleration occurs, then $V(\mathbf{r}) dv/dt$ (symbolic form) might be seen as a separate entity with energy, momentum and force, but no source now. It seems that this is a candidate for the maximum speed b . Interestingly, even though $V(\mathbf{r})$ is written as any potential, it is the electromagnetic one which supplies a photon which has no rest mass. Experimentally, it is known that photons are radiated by accelerating charges. Thus, special relativity, which seems to be completely general in terms of viewing a particle with rest mass from different constant $-v$ frames, seems to be tied to one kind of physical force-electromagnetism through the photon.

As a result, the electric and magnetic fields which “break” off when there is acceleration should be able to create a second kind of energy and momentum (namely $\frac{1}{2} \epsilon_0 \mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{E} + \frac{1}{2\mu_0} \mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{B}$ and $\frac{1}{\mu_0} \mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}$ field).

We consider these ideas here.

Two Forces and a Potential from a Source Particle

We consider a source particle which creates a potential $V(\mathbf{r})$. In principle, a charged particle may create an electrostatic potential, but a neutron is linked with the strong nuclear force and if one considered gravity as a Newtonian force, any massive particle would create a gravitational potential.

The argument we wish to make is that there seem to be two different forces present if the source particle accelerates. The first is the usual Newtonian $-\text{grad } V(\mathbf{r})$ which depends on the change of $V(\mathbf{r})$ in space. The idea seems to be that if there is constant energy at \mathbf{r}_1 , then it is described by $\frac{1}{2} m v_1^2 + V(\mathbf{r}_1)$ at \mathbf{r}_1 and by $\frac{1}{2} m v_2^2 + V(\mathbf{r}_2)$ at \mathbf{r}_2 . If this nonrelativistic energy is constant, a change in $V(\mathbf{r})$ means a change in speed and according to Newton this requires a force.

Given that $V(\mathbf{r})$ is created by a source particle with rest mass, then this source particle may be accelerated. This suggests that $V(\mathbf{r})$ (symbolic form) is like a mass multiplied by dv/dt which is a force. Thus, there is a second force in the picture, but the key point we wish to make is that its r -dependence is different than that of $-\text{grad } V(\mathbf{r})$.

- $\text{Grad } V(\mathbf{r})$ drops off much faster than $V(\mathbf{r}) dv/dt$ if $V(\mathbf{r})$ proportional to $1/r$ (positive power) ((1))

For a source particle at rest or moving at constant speed, there is essentially one kind of force (linked to $-\text{grad } V(\mathbf{r})$ or the Lorentz modified result). In the electromagnetic case, one has the electric and magnetic fields which are linked to forces, but these are dependent on gradients d/dt partial, grad partial of source terms (ϕ and \mathbf{j} , current density).

Once a particle accelerates, there are two kind of forces, the gradient dependent one and the $V(\mathbf{r}) dv/dt$ type of force. (Again $V(\mathbf{r})$ is changed by a Lorentz transformation, but we are simply labeling the second type of force by $V(\mathbf{r}) dv/dt$ even though its exact expression is somewhat different.) The point is that it drops off in r in a very different manner than the first kind of force and would be seen by an experimenter as possibly not being associated with the source particle any longer (because it does not drop fast enough).

If this piece of force (linked with some kind of energy and momentum) drops off from the source particle, then this seems like a contradiction. The source particle is called a source because it creates $V(\mathbf{r})$ and its associated forces. It seems that without a source, $V(\mathbf{r})$ cannot exist, nor can its associated force pieces linked with $-\text{grad } V(\mathbf{r})$ (or a more appropriate gradient expression). The only way to bypass this problem is to have a dichotomy, i.e a scenario in which there is both a source particle (with presumably a rest mass) with $V(\mathbf{r})$ and gradient of $V(\mathbf{r})$ associated forces and the possibility of the gradient forces as existing on their own without a source. There would be no rest mass in such a case and presumably a constant speed. The question is: Is there any reason to accept such a scenario?

Special Relativity and the Dichotomy of A Rest Mass and Non-Rest Mass Particle

A Lorentz transformation may be developed for a particle with rest mass. In the rest frame, one has m_0 at $x=0$ at t and in the moving frame: $x'/t'=v$ if the frame moves with $-v$. Given that x and t have different units and both transform, it seems one must introduce a speed parameter b which is the same as viewed from all moving frames. In fact, the Lorentz transformation is:

$$\begin{vmatrix} g(v/b) & v/b \\ v/b & g(v/b) \end{vmatrix} \quad ((2))$$

$$\text{Here: } g(v/b) = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/bb} \quad ((3))$$

It seems that b is a maximum speed and not associated with any rest mass. Then:

$$E^2 = p^2 b^2 + m_0^2 b^4 \quad ((4)) \text{ implies that: } E = pb \text{ for } m_0=0 \quad ((5))$$

$E=pb$ is of the form of a wave equation: speed=frequency * wavelength if:

$$E = \text{constant frequency and } p = \text{constant/wavelength} \quad ((6))$$

In Newtonian mechanics, a wave moves in a medium, but there is no medium here. Thus, it seems that one requires a self-wave consisting of "force" pieces to allow for Newtonian action-reaction. This seems to fit the description of the broken off piece of $V(\mathbf{r}) dv/dt$.

The question now becomes: What is $V(\mathbf{r})$? There exist the electromagnetic potential, the gravitational one (if one wished to view gravity as Newtonian, but according to Einstein's General Relativity one has curved space), the strong force mediated by gluons which have no mass and the weak force mediated by bosons with mass. Given that experimentally one sees charged particles emitting photons (which have no rest mass), then it is the photon which seems to be the candidate for the broken off $V(\mathbf{r})dv/dt$ piece of energy.

One might ask: Why should the idea of two forces and two energies only be associated with one kind of force- the electromagnetic one? Given that a photon can exist without a source, the electric and magnetic fields, which usually have their origins in a source charged particles which creates these fields from gradients of the charge and current sources, with the electrostatic potential being energy, now one requires a second type of energy which depends on the electric and magnetic fields by themselves and no source term. If this is the case, then a source charge at rest has a potential energy (electrostatic potential), but also an electric field, which in turn, must be linked with a second kind of energy. (This energy is called self-energy and is associated with the energy required to create a spherical shell of charge by doing work against the existing electric field, layer by layer.)

Special Relativistic Massless Particle

We noted that special relativity predicts a massless particle (photon) with maximum speed c in a vacuum. Given:

$$E=pc \rightarrow -Et + px = 0 \quad ((8))$$

Given that ((8)) is like a wave solution, one may have any function $F(-Et+px)$ representing such a wave (self-wave created by electric and magnetic fields).

Traditionally, waves in medium (string, water, sound) are described by sine functions because these are mathematically associated with periodicity:

$$\exp(i \theta) \quad ((9))$$

In other words, one wishes this periodicity to create the speed c in space and so one may consider electric and magnetic fields moving as:

$$\sin(-Et+px) \quad ((9))$$

Thus, the second energy E (and its momentum) p are linked mathematically with the electric and magnetic fields. In particular, one might expect a wave-equation to apply to both the electric and magnetic fields:

$$\frac{1}{c^2} \frac{d}{dt} \frac{d}{dt} \text{partial Field} - \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} \text{partial Field} = 0 \quad ((10))$$

((10)) holds for the electric and magnetic fields when there is no source, but it should also hold for sources except that 0 is replaced by all terms containing sources (charge, current). Thus, this gives a hint of Maxwell's equations.

In the case of electromagnetism, one does not simply use $-\text{grad } V(\mathbf{r} \text{ vector})$ for a moving charge because one has a 4-vector: $(0, q \phi(\mathbf{r} \text{ vector})) \rightarrow (q/c \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{r} \text{ vector}), \phi'(\mathbf{r} \text{ vector}))$.

One then writes $\mathbf{r} \text{ vector}, t$ in terms of $\mathbf{r}' \text{ vector}, t'$ using a Lorentz transformation. The "force" type terms then become:

$$\text{Electric field} = -\text{grad } \phi - \frac{d\mathbf{A}}{dt} \text{ partial} \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{B} = \text{grad} \times \mathbf{A} \quad ((11))$$

The actual forces are $q \text{ Electric field}$ and $q \mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}$, where q is a charge with a velocity vector \mathbf{v} (apart from the source of \mathbf{B}).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to argue that there seem to be two force and energy schemes associated with a potential $V(\mathbf{r})$ linked to a source with rest mass, if a source accelerates. There is the usual $-\text{grad } V(\mathbf{r})$ from Newtonian mechanics which describes how force is due to spatial changes in $V(\mathbf{r})$. {In the electromagnetic case, $V(\mathbf{r}) = \phi(\mathbf{r})$ and this transforms through a Lorentz transformation to yield A (magnetic vector potential) and $\phi'(\mathbf{r})$. These are then linked to Electric field = $-\text{grad } \phi' - d/dt \text{ partial } A$ and $B = \text{grad } \times A$. Forces are: q Electric field and $qv \times B$. Thus, forces are not so simple as $-\text{grad } V(\mathbf{r})$ in the moving frame for the electromagnetic case.} The point is there is a dropping off of the electric and magnetic fields in r (if ϕ goes as $1/r$) due to the gradients.

We suggest that if the source of $V(\mathbf{r})$ accelerates, then $V(\mathbf{r})$, representing energy, must accelerate too, suggesting a second force of the symbolic form $V(\mathbf{r})dv/dt$. The point is that this does not drop-off as gradient of $V(\mathbf{r})$ and so has a slower drop-off if $V(\mathbf{r})$ goes as $1/r$. As a result, an experimenter might consider the $V(\mathbf{r}) dv/dt$ force as being from a separate object, i.e. severed from its source. How can this be?

We suggest that special relativity predicts an object moving with speed c which is the same as seen from all frames. It is a maximum speed associated with no rest mass and satisfies $E=pc$. Thus, if one tries to create a Lorentz transformation for a particle with rest mass, one cannot do so without introducing this massless c particle. We suggest that $E=pc$ is a waveform, but a wave without a medium. This suggests forces with no source, energy and momentum. We suggest that this may be the symbolic $V(\mathbf{r}) dv/dt$ force which now exists as a self-wave particle on its own. We suggest that it is interesting that this scenario of the c particle from special relativity is associated with electromagnetism when there are various other forces like the strong and weak nuclear ones. In particular, one could derive the Lorentz transformation for a neutron which would represent a particle with rest mass, but it would still be linked with c which follows from electromagnetic theory.